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INTRODUCTION OF A NEW METHOD FOR PRODUCING CUT PAPER STENCILS FOR DYEING -- AS AN APPLIED CASE OF LASER CUTTER --

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ABSTRACT

Kimono is a traditional Japanese garment. Several types of dyeing artifices have evolved through the process of printing traditional patterns on cloth in Japan. Paper stencils can be considered merely tools used at an intermediary stage of the dyeing process. And yet another problem is that most stencil cutting craftsmen are getting older, and thus the traditional art of paper stencil cutting may be lost under present circumstances.

In this study, we explored the possibility of replacing paper stencils produced by traditional techniques with those produced by a laser cutter, and compared actually dyed textiles by using existing and new techniques, in an attempt to achieve a quality of paper stencils produced by a different method that is closer to the superb quality of traditional artifices. As a result, we were able to suggest the guidelines on materials and patterns suitable for producing the stencils with a laser cutter.

Keywords: Paper stencil, Printing, Laser-cut

INTRODUCTION

Kimono is a traditional Japanese garment. Many types of dyeing artifices have evolved through the process of printing traditional patterns on cloth in Japan. There are fewer occasions today for Japanese to wear *kimono* in daily life, as *kimono* tends to restrict body movement and is typically more expensive than other types of clothing. Paper stencils can be considered merely tools used at an intermediary stage of the dyeing process. And yet another problem is that most stencil cutting craftsmen are getting older, and thus the traditional art of paper stencil cutting may be lost under present circumstances.

From the standpoint of enhancing dyeing techniques and rationalizing production, the printing of *kimono* textiles by using new methods are also being practiced these days, including the use of silkscreen, inkjet printers, and roll-printing by textile printing machines. Another new movement in Japan is a reevaluation of the nation's traditional culture and artifices, as evidenced by a growing trend toward seeking quality goods handmade by experienced craftsmen, instead of popular mass-produced, mass-consumed goods as in the past.

In this study, we explored the possibility of reproducing the effect of paper stencils as produced using traditional techniques, by applying a newly developed technique and comparing textiles actually dyed by using existing and new techniques, in an attempt to put closer to the quality of paper stencils produced by a method other than traditional handicraft techniques to a level approaching the superb quality of traditional artifices.

Given the fact that the method of cutting stencils with a machine has already been addressed in a previous study, this study focuses on a method of producing stencils by using a laser cutter.

With regard to materials, new materials (such as synthetic fiber and WARLON) were tested in addition to existing materials made of Japanese paper. Moreover, the finish of cutting edges and the accuracy affected by the expansion/contraction of paper stencils were evaluated. A method of producing stencils by using a laser cutter was consequently devised to produce a finish closer to that afforded by the hands of craftsmen than that made possible by using the method of cutting with a machine, even though its suitability depends on the design, such as the fineness of a pattern.

PAPER STENCILS (*KATAGAMI*) FOR DYEING

ADVENT OF PRINTED TEXTILES

Evidence of marking patterns found on earthenware made using certain objects or tools dates back to prehistoric times. The woodblocks for printing were first developed in China about 2,000 years ago. Soon afterward, the method of woodblock printing on textiles began being practiced in China and India. Today, printed textiles are produced worldwide.

KATAGAMI AND STENCILS

Katagami is a widely used dyeing technique that essentially entails cutting holes on a mask in the shape of patterns, so that the pigment will only color the necessary parts when printing a textile with pigment. We also use *katagami* when using starch paste to prevent printing. This mask is made of metal or oiled paper. In ancient times, banana leaves were also used in some regions. However, Japanese *katagami* is highly evaluated as being the most sophisticated. This is because Japanese paper—the material for *katagami*—is conducive to reproducing very precise patterns.

KATAGAMI FOR DYEING IN JAPAN

History of *katagami* for dyeing

Japan's largest production center for *katagami* for dyeing is Shiroko in Suzuka City, Mie Prefecture, located about 100 kilometers east of Kyoto (Fig. 1). Shiroko retains better traditions and techniques for all processes (e.g., *kata-jigami*, *kata-hori*, *itoire*, *shabari*) involved in producing *katagami* than any other production sites in Japan. The technique of printing beautiful pictorial devices using *katagami* has a very long history. There are many varied origins of this method. According to one explanation, the method dates back to “*Fu-ki-e*” sold from about 724 to 729 A.D. “*Fu-ki-e*” refers to the pictures of worm-eaten *Fudan* cherry leaves drawn by a priest at Shiroko Kannon Temple in Ise, and sold as material for covering and decorating paper sliding doors and lamp stands.

The streets of Kyoto became a battlefield for as long as 11 years during the Ohnin War that erupted in 1467. At that time, many craftsmen working in

Kyoto's stencil printing industry fled to Shiroko, where the industry subsequently evolved.

In the 16th century, textiles stencil-printed with large patterns (called *chugata*) were used for garments and *futon* among the common people (Fig. 2). Around that time, previously expensive cotton textiles became popular and were used for printing *chugata*.

During the Edo Period, *samurai* were obligated to wear a service outfit consisting of a shoulder-piece (called *kamishimo*) covered with tiny printed patterns, and a divided skirt (Fig. 3). Stencil printing was employed to print these tiny patterns, resulting in a growing demand for such textiles. Given the protection afforded by the Kishu Domain in Kii Province that was governed by the Kishu-Tokugawa clan, the industry grew by leaps and bounds, mainly in the Shiroko and Jike districts located in present-day Suzuka City and surrounding areas.

Figure 1. Suzuka located about 100 Km east of Kyoto in Japan.

Figure 2. Left: Yukata, it was dyed by *chugata*.

Figure 3. Right: Kamishimo and the pattern of *gokusame*.

Materials for stencil paper

The three essential qualities of stencil paper used for dyeing are water resistance, durability, and little elasticity. *Shibugami* is used as stencil paper for

Japan's traditional stencil printing, and is made by bonding several sheets of *mino-washi* with persimmon tannin through the following process: When manufacturing Japanese paper, the paper material in the water is first moved vertically. This gives the paper distinctive vertical and horizontal grains. Then, the paper is bonded with persimmon tannin as adhesive agent. At this time, sheets of paper are stacked so that the grain directions alternatively differ. In other words, the first sheet is placed in the vertical grain direction, the second sheet in the horizontal grain direction, and the third sheet in the vertical grain direction for use as a contrivance. This gives the paper less elasticity. Finally, stencil paper made in this manner is spread on a wooden board and dried in the sun. Afterwards, the paper is taken into a room and suspended from the ceiling or otherwise left in a suspended state for four to five years. This is the traditional method of producing stencil paper practiced since ancient times. During and after the Meiji Period, however, the drying time was shortened by fully drying the paper in the smoke of sawn wood or similar wood burned in a special room. In this way, *shibugami* became stencil paper offering water resistance, durability, and little elasticity.

In the currently practiced process of stencil printing, synthetic stencil paper and a substitute for stencil paper called "cross pattern vinyl" are generally used. Therefore, only a very limited number of specialist craftsmen use conventional *kata-jigami*. The synthetic paper stencil is *kata-jigami* made by impregnating Japanese paper with a synthetic resin of the polyester family. Nonwoven cloth impregnated with a synthetic resin of the polyester family is used to create the cross pattern vinyl. The synthetic paper stencil is also used for making *kohon*—an original form of patterns made by stencil paper-cutting craftsmen when they produce *ise-katagami* (Fig. 5). The craftsmen make copies of the same pattern in Japanese carbon ink on *shibugami* by using *kohon*, and then cut the copies to make a paper stencil.

Figure 4. From right to left *shibugami*, synthetic stencil paper, cross pattern vinyl.

Figure 5. *Kohon* and dyed pattern.

Silkscreen is also widely used in the currently practiced process of stencil printing. Developed from Japanese paper stencils, silkscreen is made by tightening spread silk cloth or organdy onto a wooden frame, and then masking the parts thereof by using paper or acetate fiber that adheres to the silk cloth due to the effect of print ink. However, the silkscreen process requires a business investment for exclusive use. In addition, people who maintain the traditional technique express persistent opinions about conventional *kata-jigami* being better than new materials. This is because conventional *kata-jigami* enables craftsmen to demonstrate their highly sophisticated cutting skills and express the beauty of sharply outlined printed patterns created by pursuing the beauty of micro patterns.

CUTTING TECHNIQUES FOR STENCIL PAPER

Some typical stencil-resist-dyed textiles are the bold blue and white designs on cotton *yukata*, the minute patterns on silk crepe which are called *komon*, and the colorful floral designs on *yuzen*-dyed *kimono*.

SHIMABORI

The Japanese name for this technique mean “stripe cutting” (Fig. 6). The knife has a long shank that fits into a cord-bound split bamboo handle. Although this technique appears easy—because the cutter simply draws the blade the along a straight edge—in fact, it is most difficult. Even a minute inconsistency in the width of a stripe is immediately evident to the naked eye. It is not uncommon for 11hairline stripe (22 knife cut) to lie within the space of one centimeter. After they have been cut, stripe stencils are reinforced by a fine webbing of silk. This technique is called *itoire*.

TUKIBORI

The knife for *tsukibori* (which means “push cutting”) is essentially the same as that for *shimabori* except it is sharpened to a more slender point and has a longer handle (Fig.7). The knife is held with its cutting edge away from the cutter. The blade is pushed through the paper in a sawing motion over a small hole in a special cutting board. This hole allows the knife tip to penetrate freely. *Tsukibori* is used to cut a great variety of delicate floral and geometric patterns. Such stencils used to be reinforced by *itoire*, but today they are reinforced by *shabari*(silk gauze which is lacquered to one of the stencil).

DOGUBORI

The Japanese term for this technique means, “tool cutting”, but in English it might better be described as “pinch cutting” (Fig.8). *Dogubori* employs a great variety of punches to cut all kinds of shape: diamonds, ovals, crescents, squares, flower petals. The *dogubori* cutter must be an expert toolmaker since he cannot buy the tools already made. Each punch is composed of paired metal blades that are fitted together and bound to a wooden handle. Patterns produced by this technique tend to be geometric. Like *kiribori* stencil, described next, they generally need no reinforcement.

KIRIBORI

This technique is used to cut extremely fine dot patterns such as the *komon* designs favored by *samurai* (Fig.9). The cutting tool is a tiny crescent-shaped blade (like half a cylinder) that is pressed against the paper and rotated 180 degrees so as to cut out a tiny disc of paper. Extraordinarily minute patterns can be cut by this method; in one square centimeter there can be as many as one hundred.

Figure 6. Paper stencil of shimabori

Figure 7. Paper stencil of tukibori

Figure 8. Paper stencil of dogubori

Figure 9. Paper stencil of kiribori

PRODUCTION OF PAPER STENCILS BY MACHINE CARVING

A past study report publicized a method of mechanizing the production of paper stencils by preserving the sense of hand-cut stencils in the outcome. This is the Aichi University of Education Study Report No. 26 entitled, “Simulation of *Komon* (Fine Patterns) and Machine Carving of Paper Stencils -- Focusing on Conception.” The report states that the lines and surfaces on a paper stencil used for dyeing fine patterns produced by handwork comprise rows of small figures positioned with a certain irregularity in both the vertical and horizontal directions. Since such irregularity is only seen in hand-cut stencils, the patterns become more valuable. This report examined a simulation conducted with formulated *tohshi* (consecutive) patterns that were carved on the paper stencil by a numerically controlled drilling machine. In the study report, Mr. Hiroomi Rokutani, a paper stencil-cutting craftsman, gives his impression by stating, “The holes are finely cut.”

REPRODUCTION OF PAPER STENCILS FOR DYEING BY MACHINE

THE METHOD ADDRESSED IN THIS STUDY

Regarding the point about “holes being finely cut on the paper stencil” as stated in the past study report mentioned above, both the paper pattern-cutting craftsmen and dyeing craftsmen assessed that the cut edges of the paper stencil affect the finish of dyeing, and thus feel uncomfortable with cut edges. In other words, “a machine capable of precise carving cannot add charm to the stencil.” Therefore, this study adopted a laser cutter that processes patterns as analog images (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Laser cutter and cutting the pattern.

SELECTION OF MATERIAL TO BE PROCESSED

As for the material of stencil paper covered in this study, we decided to adopt synthetic paper stencils as the main material, and not traditional *shibugami*. This is because, when we interviewed the dyeing craftsmen, they stated the following: “In the process of paper stencil printing, patterns must be modularized consecutively for a length of 12 m, and then repeatedly transcribed on the textile (Fig. 11). Therefore, the paper stencil must maintain a certain degree of humidity.” And based on the results of observing the edges of laser-cut material under a microscope, we selected the aforementioned stencil paper.

Figure 11. Traditional dyeing process, He is spreading paste for reserve print on the cloth.

REPRODUCIBILITY OF PATTERNS BY LASER CUTTER

As shown in Fig.12, the cutting edges were found scorched in the case of *shibugami*, and thus a problem in dyeing was posed with regard to water resistance and durability. And when cutting cross pattern vinyl by using a laser cutter, the material melted and produced a spoiled finish, partly due to the inherent stickiness of the material (Fig. 13). Conversely, the synthetic paper in Fig.14 showed the best finish of all cut materials used experimentally in this study. This was due to the effect that polyester resin (coated on the stencil paper surface to make it water-resistant) melted on the cutting edges properly.

With regard to the types of patterns, it was found that making patterns of consecutive dots like *kiri-bori* as shown in Fig. 16 with a laser cutter entails more processing time than for other types of patterns, and that since the stencil-cutting techniques used for *kiri-bori* and *shima-bori* are intended for extremely delicate patterns, it is difficult to reproduce those techniques.

Figure 12. Left: Shibugami cutting edge.

Figure 13. Right: Cross pattern vinyl cutting.

Figure 14. Left: Synthetic paper cutting edge.

Figure 15. Right: Hand made cutting edge.

Figure 16. Kiribori(left) and shimabori(right) laser cutting edge.

CONSIDERATION

Judging from the results, reproducing the technique of consecutively cutting numerous dots like *kiri-bori* (which has 100 holes cut within the space of under 1 cm²) or patterns comprising consecutive straight lines in pursuit of the beauty of micro patterns like *shimabori* (which has 11 hairline stripe (22 knife cut) to lie within the width of 1cm) was deemed difficult using laser-cut paper stencils. It was also determined that dyeing craftsmen need to be flexible in cutting to suit the condition of stencil paper and the climate of the day, and that reproduction is difficult using the laser-cutting method that emits a laser beam on the material and burns the cutting edges to make patterns.

Regarding a relatively rougher pattern as shown in Fig. 17-20, paper stencils made by using the laser cutter can be expected to produce patterns having a charming finish, in view of the condition of the

Figure 17. Pattern1

Figure 18. Pattern2

Figure 19. Pattern3

Figure 20. Pattern4

4 patterns to produce the stencils with a laser cutter.

cutting edges, which are not possible using any other method that entails the use of a machine.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results above, we have compared the dyeing processes using a hand-cut paper stencil and a laser-cut paper stencil (Table 1-3). We tried the dyeing process using starch paste that is utilized for dyeing small patterns. The author implemented the dyeing process. In considering the types of dyeing finish, the author also selected bleached cotton and pure silk as materials to be dyed, as well as brush dyeing with a natural dye of *su-o*, dip dyeing with a chemical dye of Neothlene C Blue C-6G New (for cotton only), and dip dyeing with Dylon Multicolor 34 as dyeing methods, since the author felt that differences in any factors other than the pattern of the paper stencil might produce a different finish.

Table1-3, Comparison of the dyeing processes using a hand-cut paper stencil and a laser-cut paper stencil
 Dyeing color (Natural dye, Synthetic dye) Clothes (silk, cotton) Patterns (chidori,shouchikubai, ume,hishi-monyou)

Table1, Dyeing samples by hand made and laser cutter (su-o and silk)

	Pattern1	Pattern2	Pattern3	Pattern4
Hand made Shibugami				
Laser cutting synthetic paper				
Laser cutting Shibugami				

Table2, Dyeing samples by hand made and laser cutter (Dylon Multicolor 34 and silk)

	Pattern1	Pattern2	Pattern3	Pattern4
Hand made Shibugami				
Laser cutting synthetic paper				
Laser cutting Shibugami				

Table3, Dyeing samples by hand made and laser cutter (Neothlene C blue C-6G New and cotton)

	Pattern1	Pattern2	Pattern3	Pattern4
Hand made Shibugami				
Laser cutting synthetic paper				
Laser cutting Shibugami				

For each combination of method and dye, the author used both a hand-cut paper stencil and a laser-cut paper stencil. We presented the results of work pieces dyed with the hand-cut and laser-cut paper stencils to the stencil-cutting craftsmen and dyeing craftsmen, and then conducted a hearing. They said that it was possible to reproduce dyed (positive) patterns against a white background, white (negative) patterns against a dyed background, and *kukuri* (only the outlines are dyed and their peripherals are left undyed) patterns by using a laser-cut paper stencil.

Mr. Tomomasa Kaneda, a dyeing craftsman specializing in the fine patterns of Tokyo Kimono Dye, said that the results showing added charm regarding the cut edges cannot be produced by silkscreen or machine cutting; however, it is difficult to reproduce such a precise pattern as what is called *goku-sa-me*, which has 400 holes cut with a cone in the space of about the size of a 100 yen coin. The result of the pattern made by the line cutting technique was not satisfactory, as the lines were found to thicken after actual dyeing (Fig. 21.22).

The stencil-cutting craftsmen and dyeing craftsmen also assessed that the parts having acute angles were rounded, resulting in a lack of sharpness in the outlines of patterns, compared with those made using hand-cut stencils (Fig. 23.24).

Figure 21. Using hand cut stencil Figure 22. Using laser cut stencil

Figure 23. Using hand cut stencil Figure 24. Using laser cut stencil

CONCLUSION

In this study, we explored the possibility of replacing paper stencils produced by traditional techniques with those produced by a laser cutter, and compared actually dyed textiles by using existing and new techniques, in an attempt to achieve a quality of paper stencils produced by a different method that is closer to the superb quality of traditional artifices.

With regard to materials, we tested new materials (such as synthetic fiber and WARLON) in addition to existing materials made of Japanese paper. We also evaluated the finish of the cutting edges and the accuracy affected by the expansion/contraction of paper stencils.

As a result, we were able to suggest the guidelines on materials and patterns suitable for producing the stencils with a laser cutter.

We also found that suitability of laser-cut stencils depends on the fineness of patterns and other design factors.

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